

Faster-than-Nyquist Signaling for Next Generation Communications: Shannon Capacity, Signal Detection, and Code Design

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KPI for next generation wireless communications:

Table 1: Communication Performance Metric from 4G to 6G

KPI	4 G	5 G	6 G
Peak Throughput	100 Mbps	10 Gbps	1 Tbps
Latency	100 ms	10 ms	1 ms
User Density	10^5 device/km ²	10^6 device/km ²	10^7 device/ km ²
Spectral Efficiency	15 bps/Hz	30 bps/Hz	100 bps/Hz
Bandwidth	Max 6 GHz	Max 300 GHz	Maybe 3 THz
Mobility	350 km/h	500 km/h	1000 km/h

Objectives:

Faster-than-Nyquist (FTN) signaling is a type of **non-orthogonal signaling** for improved spectral efficiency, which aims to provide new solutions to scenarios with limited spectral resource.

FTN signaling vs. Nyquist signaling

FTN signal

- FTN signal reads

$$s(t) = \sqrt{E_s} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n]h(t - n\tau T),$$

where $0 \leq \tau \leq 1$ is the **compression factor**.

- An example of FTN signal with $[+1, -1, +1, -1, -1]$, where $\tau = 0.5$.

Shannon capacity over AWGN channels

- With a bandlimited sinc shaping pulse defined in $[-W, W]$, the Shannon capacity over AWGN channel is given by

$$C = W \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{P}{WN_0} \right) \quad \text{bits/s}$$

- For non-sinc shaping pulses, the capacity reads

$$C_{\text{PSD}} = \int_0^{\infty} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{2P}{N_0} |H(f)|^2 \right) df \quad \text{bits/s},$$

where $H(f)$ is the Fourier transform of $h(t)$.

Folded-spectrum

Folded-spectrum: Let $h(t)$ be the shaping pulse of the FTN system, whose spectrum is given by $|H(f)|^2$. The folded-spectrum is defined by

$$|H_{\text{fo}}(f)|^2 \triangleq \begin{cases} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} |H(f + \frac{k}{\tau T})|^2, & |f| \leq \frac{1}{2\tau T} \\ 0, & |f| > \frac{1}{2\tau T}. \end{cases}$$

Shannon capacity for FTN signaling over AWGN channels

FTN capacity: Given folded-spectrum $|H_{\text{fo}}(f)|^2$, the FTN capacity satisfies

$$C_{\text{FTN}} = \int_0^{\frac{1}{2\tau T}} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{2P|H_{\text{fo}}(f)|^2}{N_0} \right) df.$$

Furthermore, for non-sinc shaping pulses, we have

$$C < C_{\text{FTN}} \leq C_{\text{PSD}}$$

Introduction of FTN signaling

Figure 3.1: Spectrum of $h(t)$ with different roll-off factors β

Figure 3.2: Shannon capacity corresponding to $h(t)$ with different roll-off factors β

Introduction of FTN signaling

Figure 3.3: Comparisons among channel capacities for $\beta = 0.3$

Figure 3.4: Comparisons among spectral efficiencies for $\beta = 0.3$

Time-domain equalization for FTN signaling

Transmitter:

Receiver:

Transmit signal:

$$s(t) = \sqrt{E_s} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n] h(t - n\tau T).$$

Channel observations under AWGN channel:

$$y[n] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} r(t) h^*(t - n\tau T) dt = \sum_{m=0}^{N-1} x[m] g[m - n] + \eta[n],$$

where $\eta[n]$ is the colored noise

M-BCJR based on Ungerboeck observation model

Ungerboeck observation model:

$$P(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{x}) \propto \prod_n \varphi(y_n, \mathbf{x}),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(y_n, \mathbf{x}) &= \varphi(y_n, S_n, S_{n-1}) \\ &\triangleq \exp \left\{ \frac{2}{N_0} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ x_n^* \left(y_n - \frac{1}{2} g_0 x_n - \sum_{l=1}^{L_I} g_l x_{n-l} \right) \right\} \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

if S_{n-1} and S_n are connected in the trellis, otherwise its zero.

Properties of Ungerboeck observation model:

- State transition metric has no probabilistic meaning
- Any y_n is related to adjacent $2L_I + 1$ transmitted symbols, i.e., $x_{n-L_I}, x_{n-L_I+1}, \dots, x_{n+L_I}$.

Two reduced-complexity methods

Reduced-complexity method 1

(a) Forward recursion

(b) Backward recursion

Correct tail path

- Metric of correct tail path (CTP) determines the MAP probability.
- It has the largest metric under certain conditions.

Backward recursion

- Find the CTP
- Calculate the probability of states based on CTP

Error Performance

Figure 4.1: BER performance of the proposed algorithm with rate-half feed-forward (7,5) convolutional code and 15 Turbo iterations, where BPSK mapping is considered $\tau = 0.35$.

Figure 4.2: BER performance of the proposed algorithm with rate-half feed-forward (7,5) convolutional code and 10 Turbo iterations, where 16-QAM mapping is considered $\tau = 0.35$.

Frequency-domain equalization for FTN signaling

- Intentionally introducing cyclic prefix, altering channel matrix \mathbf{G} from a Toeplitz matrix into a circulant matrix $\bar{\mathbf{G}}$.
- Conventional operation in time becomes multiplication in frequency.

Comparison to time-domain equalization:

- Degraded error performance due to the zero-approaching eigenvalues.
- Generally requires less computational complexity.

Signal detection for FTN signaling

Figure 4.3: Eigenvalues distributions of \mathbf{G} and $\bar{\mathbf{G}}$, where $\beta = 0.3$

Figure 4.4: Performance comparisons between time-domain and frequency-domain equalizations with different β .

Code-based channel shortening for FTN signaling

Transmitter

Figure 5.1: Convolutionally encoded FTN transmitter

Receiver

Figure 5.2: FTN receiver based on code-based channel shortening (CCS) algorithm

Output retainable convolutional code

Figure 5.3: An example of output retainable convolutional code, whose generator polynomial is given by $\mathcal{G}(D) = \left[\frac{1}{1+D+D^2}, \frac{1}{D} \right]$

Detection metric modification

Original metric

$$J(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{k=0}^{L-1} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ x_{kN+i}^* \left(y_{kN+i} - \frac{1}{2} g[0] x_{kN+i} - \sum_{l=0}^{i-1} g[l] x_{kN+i-l} - \sum_{l=i}^{L_1} g[l] x_{kN+i-l} \right) \right\}.$$

Revised metric

$$\begin{aligned} J(\mathbf{x}) &\approx \hat{J}(\mathbf{x}) \triangleq \sum_{k=0}^{L-1} \gamma(S_{k+1}, y_{kN}^{kN+N-1} | S_k, \mathcal{C}) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{L-1} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ x_{kN+i}^* \left(y_{kN+i} - \frac{1}{2} g[0] x_{kN+i} \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. - \sum_{l=0}^{i-1} g[l] x_{kN+i-l} - \sum_{l=i}^{L_1} g[l] \hat{x}_k^{(L_1-l-1)} \right) \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\gamma(S_{k+1}, y_{kN}^{kN+N-1} | S_k, \mathcal{C})$ denotes the approximated metric corresponding to state transition between S_k to S_{k+1} under the code structure \mathcal{C} .

Error performance analysis

Weight spectrum

- Euclidean distance

$$D^2(\mathbf{e}) = \frac{1}{2E_b} \mathbf{e}^H \mathbf{G} \mathbf{e}$$

- Effective Euclidean distance

$$D_{\text{eff}}^2(\mathbf{e}) = \frac{1}{2E_b} \mathbf{e}^H \mathbf{T} \mathbf{e}$$

Approximated bound of event error:

With transmitted sequence \mathbf{x} , the event error probability corresponding to $\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{e}$ is approximately bounded by

$$\Pr(\mathbf{e}|\mathbf{x}) \lesssim Q \left(\sqrt{\frac{E_b}{N_0} D_{\text{eff}}^2(\mathbf{e}) \frac{D_{\text{eff}}^2(\mathbf{e})}{D^2(\mathbf{e}) + \frac{2\sigma_{\text{ISI}}^2(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{e})}{N_0}}} \right),$$

where

$$\sigma_{\text{ISI}}^2(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{e}) \triangleq \frac{1}{2E_b} \mathbb{E} \left[\mathbf{x}^H (\mathbf{G} - \mathbf{T}) \mathbf{e} \mathbf{e}^H (\mathbf{G} - \mathbf{T})^H \mathbf{x} \right],$$

denotes the residual ISI energy after Gaussian approximation.

Key points for code search

- Find code structure maximize d_{\min}^2 under given memory length
- Minimize the number of codeword pairs leading to d_{\min}^2
- Need to search all possible codeword pairs without considering all-zero codewords.

Search results

Table 2: Good output retainable convolution codes for $R = 1/2$, where $\beta = 0.3$ is considered.

τ	memory length	Generator matrix	d_{\min}^2	$d_{H,\min}$	Asymptotical coding gain
$\tau = 0.8$	3	$\left[\frac{1}{1+D+D^2}, \frac{1}{1+D} \right]$	2.46	4	0.90 dB
	4	$\left[\frac{1}{1+D+D^2}, \frac{1}{1+D^2} \right]$	2.68	5	1.27 dB
	5	$\left[\frac{1}{1+D+D^3}, \frac{1}{1+D^2} \right]$	3.27	5	2.14 dB
	6	$\left[\frac{1}{1+D^3+D^4}, \frac{1}{1+D+D^2} \right]$	3.85*	6	2.84 dB
	7	$\left[\frac{1}{1+D^3+D^4}, \frac{1}{1+D^2+D^3} \right]$	4.01*	6	3.02 dB

Search results-Con't

Table 3: Good output retainable convolution codes for $R = 1/2$, where $\beta = 0.3$ is considered.

τ	memory length	Generator matrix	d_{\min}^2	$d_{H,\min}$	Asymptotical coding gain
$\tau = 2/3$	3	$\left[\frac{1}{1+D^2}, \frac{1}{1+D} \right]$	1.85	3	1.31 dB
	4	$\left[\frac{1}{1+D+D^2}, \frac{1}{1+D^2} \right]$	2.17	5	2.00 dB
	5	$\left[\frac{1}{1+D+D^3}, \frac{1}{1+D^2} \right]$	2.70	5	2.95 dB
	6	$\left[\frac{1}{1+D^3+D^4}, \frac{1}{1+D+D^2} \right]$	3.35	6	3.88 dB
	7	$\left[\frac{1}{1+D+D^4}, \frac{1}{1+D^2+D^3} \right]$	3.52*	6	4.10 dB
$\tau = 0.5$	5	$\left[\frac{1}{1+D^2+D^3}, \frac{1}{1+D^2} \right]$	1.52	5	1.78 dB
	6	$\left[\frac{1}{1+D^2+D^4}, \frac{1}{1+D^2} \right]$	2.00*	4	2.97 dB
$\tau = 0.35$	6	$\left[\frac{1}{1+D^2}, \frac{1}{1+D+D^2+D^3+D^4} \right]$	0.74*	6	1.21 dB

Numerical Results

Detection/decoding	Number of state	Generator matrix	Memory length	Num of information bits
Joint	256	$1, \frac{1+D^2+D^3}{1+D^2}$	3	1000
Channel shortening	32	$1, \frac{1+D^2+D^3}{1+D^2}$	3	1000
CCS algorithm	32	$\left[\frac{1}{1+D^2+D^3}, \frac{1}{1+D^2} \right]$	5	1000

Figure 5.4: BER performance for CCS algorithm under $\tau = 0.5$

Design of concatenated codes for FTN signaling

Transmitter

Figure 5.5: Considered transmitter with serial concatenation

Receiver

Figure 5.6: Considered receiver with serial concatenation

Numerical results

Type	Code structure	Num states	Rate(inner code)	Rate(outer code)	Code rate	τ	length
Type A	FTN-SCCC	4	0.499	0.499	0.249	0.5	8192
	Nyquist-SCCC	4	0.666	0.749	0.499	N/A	8188
Type B	FTN-SCCC	4	0.666	0.499	0.333	0.5	8194
	Nyquist-SCCC	4	0.666	0.999	0.666	N/A	8197

Figure 5.7: BER performances of FTN-SCCC and Nyquist-SCCC under the same data rate

Self-concatenated convolutional code

Transmitter

Figure 5.8: Transmitter for FTN transmission with self-concatenated convolutional codes (SECCC).

Receiver

Figure 5.9: Receiver for FTN transmission with SECCC.

Design of self-concatenated convolutional code

Factor graph

Figure 5.10: Factor representation of SECCC coded FTN systems.

EXIT chart

Figure 5.11: EXIT chart of SECCC coded FTN system with $E_b/N_0 = 1.3$ dB.

Numerical results

Code structure	Code rate	Detection	Decoder	Iteration	τ	length
FTN-SECCC	0.499	16-state BCJR	N/A	50	2/3	64808
FTN-LDPC	0.5	32-state BCJR	50-iter SPA	50	2/3	64800
Nyquist-LDPC	0.75	N/A	50-iter	50-iter SPA	N/A	65536
Nyquist-Turbo	0.749	N/A	16-state BCJR	50	N/A	64816

Figure 5.12: BER performances of FTN-SECCC, FTN-LDPC, Nyquist Turbo, and Nyquist-LDPC, where the corresponding capacity limits are also plotted.

- FTN signaling is an important non-orthogonal transmission scheme aiming for achieving an improved spectral efficiency.
- Shannon capacity of FTN signaling is larger than that of the Nyquist signaling.
- Reduced-complexity equalization is important for practical implementation of FTN signaling.
- Code design is also important for FTN signaling, and conventional channel code designed for Nyquist cannot be directly applied to FTN systems.

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Thank you very much!